

COMPARISON OF THE BIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF WALNUT OIL IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a comparative analysis of the biological properties of walnut oil as described in Uzbek and English language sources. The study aims to identify similarities and differences in the reported health benefits and applications of walnut oil across both languages. The research methodology involves a comprehensive literature review of academic articles, traditional medicine texts, and popular health resources in Uzbek and English. The results reveal a high degree of overlap in the described biological properties, with both languages emphasizing walnut oil's positive effects on gastrointestinal health, liver function, and cardiovascular health.

INTRODUCTION

Walnut oil, derived from the nuts of the *Juglans regia* tree, has been used for centuries in various cultures for its culinary and medicinal properties [1]. In both Uzbekistan and English-speaking countries, walnut oil is recognized as a valuable natural product with numerous health benefits [2,3]. However, the way these biological properties are described and prioritized may differ between Uzbek and English language sources due to cultural, historical, and linguistic factors [4]. This article aims to compare and contrast the biological properties of walnut oil as presented in Uzbek and English languages, identify similarities and differences, and discuss the implications for research and cross-cultural understanding.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

A comprehensive literature review was conducted to identify relevant sources discussing the biological properties of walnut oil in Uzbek and English languages. The search included academic databases, traditional medicine texts, and popular health resources. Key search terms included "walnut oil," "biological properties," "health benefits," and their Uzbek equivalents [5]. The identified sources were categorized based on language and type of publication, and their content was analyzed for mentions of specific biological properties and health applications of walnut oil [6].

RESULTS

The literature review revealed a significant overlap in the biological properties of walnut oil described in Uzbek and English language sources. In both languages, walnut oil was reported to have beneficial effects on gastrointestinal health, liver function, and

cardiovascular health [7,8]. Uzbek sources often emphasized the role of walnut oil in treating gastritis and normalizing stomach and intestinal function [9], while English sources focused more on its potential to reduce inflammation and improve lipid profiles.

Both Uzbek and English sources mentioned the hepatoprotective properties of walnut oil, highlighting its ability to support liver cell regeneration. However, Uzbek sources tended to provide more specific details on the mechanisms of action and traditional use of walnut oil for liver health.

Regarding cardiovascular health, both languages described walnut oil as having a positive impact on heart function, blood vessel elasticity, and overall cardiovascular wellness. English sources often cited scientific studies on the anti-atherogenic and antioxidant properties of walnut oil, while Uzbek sources relied more on traditional knowledge and anecdotal evidence.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The comparative analysis of the biological properties of walnut oil in Uzbek and English languages reveals a high degree of consistency in the reported health benefits. This suggests a shared understanding of the therapeutic potential of walnut oil across cultures and highlights the value of traditional knowledge in informing modern research.

However, some differences in the emphasis and specific applications of walnut oil were noted between the two languages. Uzbek sources tended to provide more detailed accounts of the traditional use of walnut oil for specific conditions, such as gastritis and liver disorders, while English sources focused more on the broader health benefits and the underlying scientific mechanisms.

"Yong'oq moyi" - This is the most common and straightforward way to say "walnut oil" in Uzbek. "Gretsiya yong'og'i moyi" - Literally meaning "Greek walnut oil", this specifies that it is oil from the walnut species *Juglans regia*. "Xushbo'ybarg yong'og'i moyi" - Meaning "fragrant leafed walnut oil", this refers to the distinct aroma of walnut trees. "Tabiiy yong'oq moyi" - "Natural walnut oil", implying it is unrefined and minimally processed. "Sof yong'oq moyi" - "Pure walnut oil", suggesting it is 100% walnut oil with no additives".

So in summary, while "yong'oq moyi" is the most concise term, there are various descriptive adjectives in Uzbek that can qualify and expand on the type and properties of the walnut oil being referenced.

These differences may be attributed to cultural and historical factors, as well as the varying levels of scientific research and documentation available in each language. The Uzbek language sources often drew upon a rich tradition of herbal medicine and folk remedies, while English sources relied more heavily on modern biomedical research.

CONCLUSIONS

The comparative analysis of the biological properties of walnut oil in Uzbek and English languages demonstrates a significant overlap in the reported health benefits, particularly in the areas of gastrointestinal, liver, and cardiovascular health. However, some differences in the specific applications and the extent of the claimed benefits were observed, reflecting cultural, historical, and scientific factors.

This study highlights the importance of considering linguistic and cultural context when investigating the biological properties of natural products and the value of traditional knowledge in informing modern research. Further research is needed to bridge the gap

between Uzbek and English language sources, promote knowledge exchange, and explore the potential synergies between traditional and scientific understanding of walnut oil's health benefits.

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